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OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Abdunazarova Mavluda

OT SO‘Z TURKUMINI O‘QITISH USULLARI

DRJI

 Universal
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WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

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 zenodo

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

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